
PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF STRENGTHENING INTERPERSONAL RELATIONS IN FAMILIES

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Abstract.

In this article, the study of interpersonal relationships is one of the most pressing problems in the field of psychology. has been the subject of research by several foreign psychologists on the subject of secrecy.

Keywords.

Interpersonal relationships, intrapsychological category, human relationships, generality, similarity, harmony, socio-psychological phenomenon, ontogeny, parent and child, perceptual communication, art, personality.

Introduction

Human relations are the processes of interaction in which interpersonal relations are formed and manifested. Interpersonal relations mean the process of interaction, communication and dealing between people. The study of interpersonal relations is one of the most urgent problems in psychology. Because communication, which is one of the most influential and leading activities of the human personality, and mutual relations through it, lead to the emergence of qualities such as commonality, similarity, and harmony among people. Especially in the family environment, the specific aspects of interpersonal relations, for example, the relations between parents and children, directly affect the effectiveness and content of a person's life, activities.

Therefore, the issue of studying interpersonal relations between people and their various psychological characteristics is one of the most important current problems in the science of social psychology. Communication is a form of interpersonal relations, with the help of which people enter into psychological contact with each other, exchange information, influence, be affected, perceive, understand and evaluate processes. Therefore, treatment is a socio-psychological phenomenon, a social category that directly participates in all spheres of social life

and emerges as an objective and subjective need that reflects the material, spiritual, emotional, cognitive, motivational, and regulatory aspects of cooperative activity. acts as the main factor, the basis.

Literature Analysis And Methodology

Psychologists L.S. Vygotsky, S.L. Rubinstein, A.N. Leontev, B.G. Ananev, A.V. Zaporozhets, A.A. Bodalev, B.F. Lomov, A.A. Leontev, M.I. Lysina conducted research (39, 58,103). L.S. Regarding the importance of communication in the development and development of the mental world of a child's personality, Vygotsky said: "The main way for a child to manifest his personal activity is his communication with adults. His attitude towards the outside world is always through another person.

Results

L.S. According to Vygotsky, the genetic primary interaction in ontogenesis is argument, dialogue; and the second is the individual's consciousness, the individuality of mental processes: "We can express the general genetic law of cultural development in the following form: in the cultural growth of a child, any function appears twice, in two different plans, to be evaluated, first social, then psychological, as well as , as an interpersonal interpsychological category and then as an intrapsychological category in the child's inner world". L.S. Vygotsky also points out that the main weapon and tool in interpersonal relationships is the process of communication. In his opinion, in interpersonal relations, first, communication is the main tool, and then behavior is the tool. Because, even when a person is alone, he retains the function of dealing.

L.S. Another aspect of Vygotsky's views is that behavior is manifested in the forms of internalization, that is, internal speech, and externalization, that is, external speech and behavior. It can be seen that due to treatment, personalization occurs. So, L.S. Vygotsky's thoughts on the psychology of behavior and interpersonal relations are extremely valuable, because in it we see behavior as an important basis for the process of socialization of a person, and we further understand that the value of this process in the formation of a person is infinite (58). V.M. In Bekhterev's rich heritage, the problem of interpersonal relations, in particular, the subject of behavior, was studied from the perspective of socio-psychological theory. In his views, the interaction of people is interpreted as an important problem.

V.M. Bekhterev describes the role of communication in social life and interprets its functions as a mechanism for implementing cooperative activities. In

his opinion, the more diverse and rich a person's interactions with those around him are, the more successful his development will be. V.M. In analyzing the social role and function of behavior, Bekhterev focuses on the importance of imitation and influence, which are its manifestations. In his opinion, if there was no imitation, there would be no personality. Because imitation means that it takes its material out of circulation. Influence is considered as a factor of manifestation of social processes. V.M. Bekhterev conditionally divides communication into direct and indirect types. If it takes a letter, phone, telegram, caressing, fighting, etc. as components of indirect communication, it includes speech in the type of direct communication. It should be noted that the work of experimental study of behavior by V.M. It was done by Bekhterev.

V.N. According to Myasishev's concept of "Relational Psychology of the Person", the "dialogic" character of the person is manifested as a product of personal experience and interaction with other people. Due to this, the internal power of a person, such as the level of interest, emotional strength, desire, need, social direction, is formed in a person, and this is expressed in his experiences, behavior, and actions. V.N. From the analysis of Myasishev's works on the psychology of interpersonal relations, it can be seen that the process of communication develops not only from the influence of the characteristics, character, inclinations and abilities of the individual, but is also manifested in connection with the mental processes of the participants in the communication. Therefore, V.N. A special aspect of Myasishev's works is clearly visible in the relationship between behavior, its psychological structure and the mental processes of the participants in the dialogue. GM In the book "Social Psychology", Andreyeva proposes a structure of 3 different tasks and complex processes that occur in interpersonal relations.

1. The communicative side of communication, that is, as a process of interaction or exchange of information between participants in communication;

2. The interactive side of communication, that is, as a process of influencing the behavior of those who enter into communication;

3. The perceptive side of communication, that is, as a process related to the perception and understanding of the participants of communication. B.F. that communication in relationships is psychologically complex. Parigin writes: "Communication is such a multifaceted process that it simultaneously includes:

- A) the process of interaction of individuals;

- B) the process of information exchange between individuals;

- V) the process of one person's attitude towards another person;
- G) the process of one person influencing others;
- D) the opportunity to sympathize with each other;
- Y) the process of mutual understanding of individuals".

So, as interpersonal relations, that is, communication process, is characterized by the most complexity and versatility among the activities performed by people, a lot of research by world psychologists in the field of social psychology shows that this phenomenon is necessary for the individual, both simple and complex. They look at it as mysterious. The family as a small group forms a whole system. The parts of this integrated system, i.e., the interpersonal relations between its members, are reflected in the family's stability, development, role in children's upbringing, etc. Western social psychologists paid great attention to the study of interpersonal relations in small groups in the years after the Second World War. In the West, especially in the USA, many directions have appeared in the process of studying interpersonal relations; G. Zimmel, G. Cooley, later R. Bales, D. Cartwright, G. Homans, S. Ash, R. Crutchfield, et al. The specific aspects of simultaneous relations of interdependent people, as well as the problem of mutual perception of people in mutual relations, have been comprehensively studied that are important in interpersonal relations. It was found that "likeability" plays a big role in interpersonal relationships for people to live in harmony and harmony, which causes them to become attached to each other.

The hypothesis put forward by the American psychologist G. Homans about the existence of a correct relationship between interpersonal cohesion and the number of communication in interpersonal relationships, the level of repetition, the level of activity, has been studied by many researchers. In Western social psychology, interpersonal relationships are viewed as an emotional phenomenon. Dj. Research by Moreno on the attractiveness and attractiveness of individuals in mutual relations with the help of sociometric research gave a strong impetus. When studying mutual compatibility in interpersonal relations, M. Shaw distinguishes this psychological state into two types.

1. Adaptations arising from needs, that partners are forced to adapt to each other in order to satisfy their mutual material and spiritual needs.

2. Conformity resulting from similarity of behavior (behavior) is the reason for the adaptation of the similarity in the actions and behavior of partners. Artistic and visual arts are used in the formation of an individual as a person, his character

traits, plays an important role in the composition of worldviews, values and many other aspects.

V.B. According to Blok, fine art can create various affective feelings in a person. For example, an artist can experience two different (ambivalent) emotions by looking at the painting depicting Ivan Grozny, the murderer of his own child, Repin; on the one hand, there is a feeling of pity for the son and father who are victims of a tragic situation, and on the other hand, there is a feeling of hatred for the father who killed the child. There is enough information in the scientific literature about the effect of art on a person that cleanses him of negative experiences, thoughts and fantasies (catharsis). Aristotle was one of the first to comment on this two and a half thousand years ago. Our contemporary Russian psychologist Yu.G. Klimenko attaches great importance to the place of art in psychotherapy: "Ultimately, the real purpose of the existence of the theater is the process of spiritual purification and catharsis." As a result of visual art affecting the subconscious of a person, it has been determined that strong emotional experiences appear in the psyche, which in turn causes a person to experience a state of hypnosis ladi This feature of fine art allows it to be used as a method of treatment for various mental, nervous and psychosomatic diseases.

Discussion

Family problems are extremely relevant in world psychology. For many years, psychological scientists from abroad, Russia and the CIS have studied the development of a person, all his achievements in the family, the genetic and acquired characteristics of the family as a special research subject. G.M. Breslav specially studied the emotional relationships in the family in the formation of the child's personality, according to him, the normal functioning of the relationship between the parents and the child in the family and, moreover, between all the members of the family, the feelings of understanding, affection, love in the relationship between them depending on availability. Therefore, he emphasizes that the formation of personality from childhood is related not only to the child, but also to his parents. A.G. Volkov's series of works are explained by the special study of the family institution from a demographic point of view. In this, the author points out that the demographic change of the family and the emergence of new family types should focus on social, economic, and psychological aspects, because of this, the process of change in the characteristics of family upbringing will occur. V. Garbuzov, I.A. Dvoymenny, R.M. In the works of psychologists like Kapralova, they emphasize that some defects in family education do not arise by themselves,

and the importance of paying attention to the influence of parents as educators and their personal examples. S.V. In Kovalev's book "Psychology sovremennoy semi", we can see that the family, the factors of family building, various periods of youth crisis in the child's personality, and the emotional relationships that arise in the child are expressed. V.P. Levkovich, E.I. The works of Pavlovich, V. L. Titarenko are also focused on the problems of the family environment, parental relations, and the impact of mutual relations on the child. Above, we quoted from the scientific works of some foreign and Russian scientists. Therefore, foreign and Russian psychologists have widely studied various aspects of communication and interpersonal relations, as well as the influence of interpersonal relations in the family on the development of the child's personality. The issue of interpersonal relations is one of the issues studied and researched in the scientific works of psychologists of Uzbekistan. We observe that Davletshin approached the issue of interpersonal relations in relation to conflicts arising in the family environment and their nature. G'.B. It is observed that Shoumarov also researched the problems that arise between husband and wife, mother-in-law and daughter-in-law, parents and children in family relations in the organization of the family, its type, in his works. The author's book "Love and Family" contains observations on conflicts and disagreements that may occur in family relations and their manifestation in the relations between parents and children. According to him, the following types of disagreements arise in the relationship between parents and children:

1. Differences in worldviews between parents and children;
2. Children should follow their own discretion in organizing their free time, choosing their own friends, demanding their independence in emotional relationships, following their own opinions in dressing, behavior, choosing a profession, family they try to have their own opinion in matters of construction, especially in the matter of choosing a future spouse;
3. Observed deviations in the behavior of parents in front of their children and others, i.e. violation of social norms, observation of alcoholism and vices;
4. In the upbringing of their children, parents are indifferent to the work of teaching their children to work, and as a result, they are used to living an easy life;
5. Superficial views of some young people on the issue of filial duty;
6. Disagreements arising as a result of insufficient levels of psychological and pedagogical knowledge in parents.

The national characteristics of the Uzbek family and their influence on the upbringing of young people were studied in the works of M.G.Davletshin,

G.B.Shoumarov. It is noted that there are questions of hierarchy, mutual respect and attention between generations, and the decisive importance of parents' opinion in building a family. In the works of V. M. Karimova, we observe detailed scientifically based information about the psychological system of the communication process, the essence and tasks of its communicative, interactive and perceptive aspects, types, forms, stages of communication, verbal and non-verbal means. In the doctoral research of the author, interpersonal relations that occur in the family environment, and the features of their influence on the perception of the family were specially studied. V.M. Karimova, F.A. In Akramova's work, the role of interpersonal communication in human development, psychological means of human communication and communication are studied in terms of the psychology of effective influence. E.G. In Ghaziyev's scientific works, communication and understanding of national identity are comprehensively described from the research history of communication, communication and speech, communication as a cooperative activity, practical issues of communication. In the research conducted by the author, the need to use the scientific views and exemplary thoughts of the thinkers of the past in the proper conduct of family relations is emphasized. In the scientific works of N.A. Soginov, the impact of husband and wife relations on family stability in the Uzbek family, the ethnopsychological characteristics of conflicts that may arise in their relations, and their impact on the child were studied. M.S. Salayeva studied the socio-psychological features of the relationship between parents and children in Uzbek families. In G.J. Berdiyev's scientific works, the specific characteristics of interpersonal relations among elementary school students were researched on the example of children with retarded mental development. However, the influence of the interactions in the family environment on the mental development of the child has not been reported. M. Yoldoshev's book "Psychological environment in the family and its impact on upbringing" raises a number of problems, such as the need to take into account young periods in the upbringing of a child, the spiritual aspects of upbringing, the influence of educational institutions on a person. G. T. Yadgarova's scientific works specifically studied the socio-psychological features of the dysfunctional family type, the evaluations of children in dysfunctional families to themselves and their mothers, and the spiritual, spiritual and educational influence of the mother in this family. P.S. Ergashev's scientific works specifically studied the issues of the duration of the first impression about a person in conditions where active interaction does not occur and the relationship does not continue. However, the specific aspects of the

influence of interpersonal relations in the family on the child's social perception have not been interpreted.

CONCLUSION

In the scientific works of F.R. Rozikov, the socio-psychological complications of divorce in the Uzbek family, the impact of divorce on the formation of the personality of the child raised in the family, the problems of conflicts in family relationships and the escalation of conflict situations are presented in scientific research. However, in scientific research, the characteristics of the influence of interpersonal relations on the social perception of children on family stability are not included in the subject of special research. From this brief analysis, it can be seen that despite the fact that interpersonal relations, the relationship between parents and children in the family environment, is a studied and researched topic, there are many aspects of it, including the child and father in the family environment. - behavior between mothers, the influence of practical and emotional aspects in mutual relations, the development characteristics of the child in the family according to these aspects, the attitude of the child in the family to his family life according to the relationship of the parents have not been studied. Therefore, in this monograph, we tried to show the relationship that parents feel and show in practice towards their children, as well as the psychological characteristics of the children's feelings towards their parents. Pedagogical education cluster: problems and solutions Due to the fact that the issue of relations between parents and children has always been relevant, we have tried to develop appropriate recommendations by monitoring possible disagreements between them. So, by reviewing the works of many scientists, we observed that the family place and the problems related to it have been scientifically researched, which indicates that family issues are extremely important issues for every nation.

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